

Solutions: Network Meta-Analysis Using R Package netmeta

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R packages

We use R functions from R package **netmeta** in this practical which is an add-on package to **meta**.

```
library("netmeta")
settings.meta(digits = 2, digits.se = 3)
```

Parkinson dataset

We utilize the Parkinson dataset from R package **netmeta**.

Load the Parkinson data and look at the format of the data.

```
data(Franchini2012)
head(Franchini2012, 2)

##           Study Treatment1    y1 sd1  n1 Treatment2    y2  sd2  n2
Treatment3
## 1 Lieberman 1998    Placebo -1.22 3.7  54 Ropinirole -1.53 4.28  95
<NA>
## 2 Lieberman 1997    Placebo -0.70 3.7 172 Pramipexole -2.40 3.40 173
<NA>
##   y3 sd3 n3
## 1 NA  NA NA
## 2 NA  NA NA
```

The data set is in wide arm-based format, i.e., each row corresponds to a single study. Both Lieberman studies compared two treatments, accordingly entries for the third treatment arm 'y3', 'sd3' and 'n3' are missing.

```
View(Franchini2012)
```

Transform data set

Transform data from wide arm-based format to contrast-based format.

```
p3 <- pairwise(list(Treatment1, Treatment2, Treatment3),
  n = list(n1, n2, n3), mean = list(y1, y2, y3), sd = list(sd1, sd2, sd3),
  data = Franchini2012, studlab = Study)
head(p3, 2)

##      TE      seTE      studlab treat1      treat2  n1 mean1 sd1  n2
mean2
## 1 0.31 0.6680897 Lieberman 1998 Placebo Ropinirole  54 -1.22 3.7  95 -
1.53
## 2 1.70 0.3826406 Lieberman 1997 Placebo Pramipexole 172 -0.70 3.7 173 -
```

```

2.40
##      sd2          Study Treatment1    y1 sd1.orig n1.orig Treatment2    y2
## 1 4.28 Lieberman 1998    Placebo -1.22    3.7    54 Ropinirole -1.53
## 2 3.40 Lieberman 1997    Placebo -0.70    3.7   172 Pramipexole -2.40
##      sd2.orig n2.orig Treatment3 y3 sd3 n3
## 1      4.28      95      <NA> NA  NA NA
## 2      3.40     173      <NA> NA  NA NA

```

Which effect measure is utilized in the analysis?

```
gs("smcont")
```

```
## [1] "MD"
```

The mean difference is used as effect measure (variable 'TE' is equal to the difference between variables 'mean1' and 'mean2'). Negative values indicate that the first intervention is more effective.

Network meta-analysis

Next, conduct a random effects network meta-analysis with placebo as reference treatment using the R object created with *pairwise*.

```

net6 <- netmeta(p3, common = FALSE, ref = "plac")
net6

## Number of studies: k = 7
## Number of pairwise comparisons: m = 9
## Number of observations: o = 1613
## Number of treatments: n = 5
## Number of designs: d = 5
##
## Random effects model
##
## Treatment estimate (sm = 'MD', comparison: other treatments vs 'Placebo'):
##           MD          95%-CI      z  p-value
## Bromocriptine -0.52 [-1.46; 0.41] -1.09  0.2736
## Cabergoline   -0.82 [-1.85; 0.20] -1.58  0.1144
## Placebo       .         .         .         .
## Pramipexole   -1.81 [-2.46; -1.16] -5.45 < 0.0001
## Ropinirole    -0.48 [-1.43; 0.48] -0.98  0.3259
##
## Quantifying heterogeneity / inconsistency:
## tau^2 = 0; tau = 0; I^2 = 0% [0.0%; 79.2%]
##
## Tests of heterogeneity (within designs) and inconsistency (between
designs):
##           Q d.f. p-value
## Total          2.29   4  0.6830
## Within designs  1.61   2  0.4473
## Between designs 0.68   2  0.7121

```

How many treatments and trials are included?

```
net6$n
## [1] 5
net6$k
## [1] 7
```

How many of them are multi-arm trials?

```
table(net6$narms)
##
## 2 3
## 6 1
```

How many and which designs occur?

```
net6$designs # List of designs
## [1] "Bromocriptine:Cabergoline"
"Bromocriptine:Placebo:Pramipexole"
## [3] "Bromocriptine:Ropinirole"          "Placebo:Pramipexole"
## [5] "Placebo:Ropinirole"
```

How many and which direct pairwise comparisons are given?

```
with(net6, table(paste0(treat1, sep.trts, treat2)))
##
## Bromocriptine:Cabergoline      Bromocriptine:Placebo
Bromocriptine:Pramipexole
##                2                1
1
## Bromocriptine:Ropinirole      Placebo:Pramipexole
Placebo:Ropinirole
##                2                2
1

net6$A.matrix
##
## Bromocriptine      Bromocriptine Cabergoline Placebo Pramipexole Ropinirole
## Bromocriptine          0          2          1          1          2
## Cabergoline           2          0          0          0          0
## Placebo               1          0          0          2          1
## Pramipexole           1          0          2          0          0
## Ropinirole            2          0          1          0          0
```

Network graph

Draw the network using a circular layout. By default, line width is proportional to the number of studies providing direct comparisons.

```
netgraph(net6, points = TRUE, cex.points = 4, cex = 1.5,
  number.of.studies = TRUE)
```


Now, use the argument 'iterate = TRUE'.

```
netgraph(net6, points = TRUE, cex.points = 4, cex = 1.5,
  number.of.studies = TRUE, iterate = TRUE)
```


Optional: You can create 3-D plots using the **rgl** library.

```
# install.packages("rgl")
# netgraph(net6, dim = "3d", col = 1)
```

Forest plots

Produce a forest plot with the default settings.

```
forest(net6)
```


The variable 'k' stored in net6 contains the number of direct comparisons. We can plot them in the forest plot and sort by decreasing treatment effect.

```
forest(net6, sortvar = TE,  
leftcols = c("studlab", "k"),  
leftlabs = c("Drug", "Direct\nstudies"),  
xlab = "Response to treatment")
```


Now, generate a forest plot with pramipexole, i.e., the most effective treatment, as reference treatment.

```
forest(net6, ref = "pram",
  label.left = "Favours other treatment",
  label.right = "Favours Pramipexole")
```


Finally, generate a forest plot of pramipexole compared to other treatments as reference.

```
forest(net6, ref = "pram", baseline = FALSE,
  label.left = "Favours Pramipexole",
  label.right = "Favours other treatment")
```


Using argument 'baseline.reference = FALSE' we get all comparisons of pramipexole with another treatment. Without this argument, comparisons are 'other treatment' vs Pramipexole. We observe that pramipexole is more effective than all other treatments but carbergoline.